

Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and phenanthrene derivatives in long-term stored bark and wood waste

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This study examined the levels of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and phenanthrene derivatives in bark and wood waste (BWW) from the Syktyvkar LDK landfill using HPLC-FLD/DAD and GC/MS methods. The waste over a period of approximately 1950 to 2010. BWW samples were taken from two cores at depth of up to 27 meters.

Significant levels of PAHs and phenanthrene derivatives were detected in the BWW (figure). Naphthalene and acenaphthene were evenly distributed throughout the profile of both cores. The content of heavy PAHs and derivatives increased sharply in the lower part of the profiles, probably due to their pedogenic formation during the waste decomposition under conditions of high temperature and high substrate moisture. These conditions promote the reductive condensation processes involving lignin, humic acids, and resin acids. An inverse relationship was observed in the accumulation of PAHs and phenanthrene derivatives in the lower layers of the BWW landfill. The elevated concentrations of heavy PAH structures and derivatives in the upper part of the profile of core 1 may be associated with combustion processes. Principle Component Analysis revealed that the accumulation of PAHs and phenanthrene derivatives depended primarily on the pH and moisture content of the waste, primarily in well 2. A greater number of the compounds studied were detected under conditions of high moisture content and neutral pH. In the lower layers of the BWW, the total toxicity equivalency concentration exceeded the maximum permissible concentrations for benz[a]pyrene in soils by up to ninefold. The upper layers exhibited a low degree of environmental risk to living organisms and natural ecosystems, whereas the lower layers presented a moderate degree of risk.

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